

Research Article

In Vitro Evaluation of Antifungal Activity of Series of 2-Phenyl-3-(6-aryl-7H-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazin-3-yl)-4H-4-chromenone Compounds

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ABSTRACT

A new series of 2-phenyl-3-(6-aryl-7H-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazin-3-yl)-4H-4-chromenone 1(a-j) has been synthesized by the reaction of 3(4-amino-5-sulfanyl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-2-phenyl-4H-4-chromenone with a variety of phenacyl bromides in ethanol under reflux. The compound with the 4-bromophenyl (1g) greatest anti *A. niger* action, while compound (1a) had the least. Except for 1a and 1i, these compounds also shown efficacy against *Candida albicans*. While others showed moderate to good action, the compound containing the 4-methoxyphenyl (1c) good activity against *C. albicans*.

INTRODUCTION

Triazoles are the class of heterocyclic compounds¹ theirazole ring is readily able to bind with a variety of enzymes and receptors in biological system *via* diverse non-covalent interactions, and thus display versatile biological activities. Among the triazoles, 1,2,4-triazole have drawn great attention due to its wide variety of activities², many drugs which containing triazole moiety available in market such as antifungal drugs myclobutanil³, tebuconazole⁴, posaconazole⁵, Itraconazole⁶, fluconazole⁷ and paclobutrazole⁸, anticancer drugs anastrozole⁹,

litroazole¹⁰ and vorozole¹¹, antimigrain drug rizatriptan¹² and antiviral drug ribavirin¹³.

The 1,2,4-triazole substituted with amino and mercapto groups have been reported to possess a variety of biological activities such as antibacterial¹⁴, antifungal¹⁵, antitubercular¹⁶, anticancer¹⁷, diuretic¹⁸, and hypoglycemic¹⁹. The amino and mercapto groups are readymade nucleophilic centers for synthesis of fused heterocyclic systems²⁰. Further, the triazole fused with thiadiazine have promising biological activities such as anti-HIV²¹, CNS stimulant²², antifungal²³, and anti-inflammatory²⁴ and anti-*Candidal* activity²⁵.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Using the cup-plate method²⁶, the compounds (**figure 1**) **1(a-j)** were further tested for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* at 100 g/mL. These compounds antifungal efficacy was compared to that of the accepted reference drug, Amphotericin B. The zones of inhibition that formed are shown in **Table 1** and are measured in millimeters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Antifungal activity**

Using the cup-plate method²⁶, the compounds **1(a-j)** were further tested for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* at 100 g/mL. These compounds antifungal efficacy was compared to that of the accepted reference drug, Amphotericin B. The zones of inhibition that formed are shown in **Table 1** and are measured in millimeters. All of the compounds had antifungal activity against *A. niger*, according to the antifungal screening findings. The compound with the 4-bromophenyl (**1g**) had the greatest anti *A. niger* action, while compound (**1a**) had the least. Except for **1a** and **1i**, these compounds also shown efficacy against *Candida albicans*. While others showed moderate to good action, the compound

containing the 4-methoxyphenyl (**1c**) good activity against *C. albicans*.

Figure 1: A new series of 2-phenyl-3-(6-aryl-7H-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazin-3-yl)-4H-4-chromenone compounds 1(a-j).

Table 1: Antifungal Activity of Compounds 1(a-j)

Compound	Ar	Zones of inhibition (mm) at 100 g/MI	
		<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
1a	Phenyl	9	—
1b	4-methylphenyl	13	9
1c	4-methoxyphenyl	12	14
1d	3-methoxyphenyl	10	10
1e	4-chlorophenyl	12	13
1f	3,4-dichlorophenyl	10	11
1g	4-bromophenyl	17	10
1h	4-nitrophenyl	14	12
1i	3-nitrophenyl	12	—
1j	4-hydroxyphenyl	10	12
Amphotericin B	—	18	16

A new series of 2-phenyl-3-(6-aryl-7H-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazin-3-yl)-4H-4-chromenone **1(a-j)** has been synthesized by the reaction of 3(4-amino-5-sulfanyl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-2-phenyl-4H-4-chromenone with a variety of phenacyl bromides in ethanol under reflux.²⁷ The compound with the 4-bromophenyl (**1g**) greatest anti *A. niger* action, while compound (**1a**) had the least. Except for **1a** and **1i**, these compounds also shown efficacy against *Candida albicans*. While others showed moderate to good action, the compound containing the 4-methoxyphenyl (**1c**) good activity against *C. albicans*. The investigated compounds' activity, however, are lower than those of the commonly used standard antibacterial agent.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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